

The effectiveness of distance Arabic learning for Indonesian speakers using YouTube channels

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ABSTRACT

Online Arabic learning presents several challenges, one of which is the ineffective utilization of learning media. This study aims to describe the tendency of Arabic learners through the Dars Arabi YouTube channel video media and the relationship between the learner's propensity and the variables of gender, age, and educational background of Dars Arabi channel users. This study uses a descriptive statistical method. The sample selection was taken randomly from as many as 160 people from a population of around 17,800 YouTube channel subscribers. This study's findings indicate that the tendency of online Arabic learners is at a moderately average level. This study also shows no statistically significant difference between trends in YouTube channel users and the variables of gender, educational background, and users' age. This study's conclusion shows the importance of using YouTube media to learn Arabic with content that is fun and can be enjoyed by all groups of society in a relaxed manner.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In today's modern era, information technology plays an important role in human life. Almost all areas of human life cannot be separated from the use of technology, including in the world of education [1]. In the world of foreign language education, information technology can also be used as a medium for learning so that the process can be carried out more effectively [2]. Technology can be used to practice language skill building, so learners can participate in learning communities with fellow learners from around the world [3]. Technology can also be used to design distance learning, and the results can be used effectively to teach virtual listening and speaking skills [4]. The use of technology-based teaching approaches can help learners effectively carry out communication activities [5]. Thus, the existence of technology has benefited human life.

However, the world of Arabic language learning is still unable to take full advantage of technological advances. The difficulty of learning Arabic is still felt by learners, among others, due to the unavailability of adequate learning facilities, including not using information technology media optimally [6]. Data shows that learning Arabic online is not effective; this happens because the learning process does not use interesting media [7]. Among the difficulties that distance learning has encountered in the assessment process [8]. Similarly, the majority of millennials find learning Arabic uninteresting due to the medium's incompatibility with their learning styles [9]. This presents a challenge for observers of Arabic language education, both individuals and

institutions, to innovate and develop learning models in accordance with the demands of the times. Arabic teachers are required to find alternative learning models that are more attractive to students, including using information technology [10], [11].

YouTube media is considered one of the media widely used by the public to find the information they need. Statistical data shows that YouTube users in Indonesia reach more than 93 million people. YouTube's use in world learning has increased significantly in the COVID-19 pandemic era [12]. Therefore, the use of YouTube media in learning is a necessity, including learning Arabic. One of the YouTube channels that is in great demand by users is Dars Arabi. The number of subscribers to date has reached more than 17,900 people (last updated, March 10, 2021). The Dars Arabi channel presents Arabic content in a pleasant manner that aligns with the interests of millennials. Learning content plays a significant role in supporting the Arabic learning process [13].

The Dars Arabi channel is a YouTube channel that provides Arabic learning content from scratch. This channel is intended for Arabic learners in Indonesia because the language of instruction used is Indonesian. The videos presented in this channel are effortless in duration that is not long, ranging from 5 to 15 minutes. The content also varies, including vocabulary with examples of usage, easy grammar rules enriched with examples, practical and thematic dialogues and several themes. The learning videos on this channel are also equipped with various simple exercises that are responded to and corrected directly by the management team as feedback on where evaluation should be in learning. The Dars Arabi channel is also equipped with interesting exercises so that learning Arabic through the YouTube channel becomes more interactive in line with modern language learning theory. Dars Arabi channel users do not only come from students but also various community groups [14]. This statement is based on the data as in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 shows that the Dars Arabi channel is in great demand by Arabic language learners from various countries. This article aims to complement previous studies' shortcomings, specifically the Arabic language learning model through the Dars Arabi YouTube media channel. In detail, the purpose of this study is to describe i) the tendency of Arabic learners through the Dars Arabi channel YouTube video media and ii) to analyze the relationship between the learner's tendency and the variables of gender, age, and educational background of the users of the Dars Arabi channel. Thus, this study's results can be used to solve the problems of learning Arabic online, especially in the COVID-19 era. The Arabic learning process through the YouTube channel can be used as an example for teachers to develop learning media to make it more attractive and favoured by students.

Many previous studies have been carried out, among them by Onisabi and Alaso [16]. Their research shows that the subject working in learning Arabic YouTube is more effective in increasing the communicative competence of Arabic. Meanwhile, in his research results, Al Kidam [17] shows that the level of mastery of Arabic for students learning using YouTube is moderate, both in listening and speaking skills.

Figure 1. Dars Arabi channel display [15]

Other research related to the impact of learning using YouTube media conducted by Al-Abdallat [18] shows that learning English using YouTube and Facebook positively impacts Jordan University students' English skills. YouTube videos are one of the most widely used media in the world, including Indonesia. Other research data also shows that YouTube is an alternative media that can be used by teachers in learning Arabic [19].

In general, previous research is still general in nature, examining learning through YouTube media for English. Previous research on Arabic continues to emphasize the importance of using YouTube media, conducted formally in the classroom. Meanwhile, this research's object is Arabic learning, carried out informally outside the classroom, where YouTube users voluntarily participate in learning through the Dars Arabi channel without coercion from anywhere. So, the novelty of this study is to show the effectiveness of Arabic learning through YouTube channels, which are followed by learners who have strong motivations from their own people.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is statistical-descriptive, aiming to manage and present data to provide an overview of the themes being studied through the data obtained [20]. This study focuses on two types of variables, namely the independent and dependent variables. The independent variables include the gender, educational background, and age of the respondents. In comparison, the dependent variable includes the tendency of YouTube Dars Arabi channel users to learn Arabic, as shown by the respondents' assessments of each item and all questionnaire items.

In this study, data was obtained by distributing online questionnaires containing all instrument items tested for reliability to all YouTube Dars Arabi channel subscribers. The questionnaire contains 10 statements to explore data related to the tendency of Arabic learners through YouTube video media and the relationship between the learner's tendency and the variables of gender, age, and educational background of YouTube users of the Dars Arabi channel. The retrieval of data in this study uses a simple random sampling technique, which involves taking data randomly from all Dars Arabi YouTube Channel subscribers who fill out the questionnaire regardless of their background [21].

The population of this research is people who are learning Arabic using the Dars Arabi YouTube media channel. Users of these channels come from all walks of life. The sample was selected randomly, with 160 customers from a population of more than 17,800 customers. The research sample is described in the following demographic Table 1. The Table 1 shows that most of the study samples were female, namely as much as 51.2%, while male gender was 48.8% of the study sample. From the Table 1, it is known that as many as 53.5% of the sample were less than 20 years old, 28.3% between 20 and 30 years old and as many as 18.1% were over 30 years old. The Table 1 also shows the educational background of Arabic learners who use the Dars Arabi channel, as many as 81.1% of the respondents have tertiary education and only 18.9% have a junior high school education or madrasah tsanawiyah and high school or madrasah aliyah.

Testing the instrument's validity was carried out by questioning the questionnaire items in the instrument according to the scientific concept [22]. In this case, the questionnaire items in the instrument were consulted with experts in Arabic language teaching, which can be concluded that the instrument questionnaire items were declared valid. Validity testing is carried out using the SPSS program. The calculation results areas in the following Table 2.

The Table 2 shows that all instrument items have been declared valid because the r count is greater than the r Table 2. Instrument reliability testing was carried out with the Cronbach Alpha formula because the data was interval data. If the Cronbach's Alpha value is >0.60 , then the questionnaire is declared reliable; if the Cronbach's Alpha value is <0.60 , the questionnaire is declared unreliable. After testing, the results show that Cronbach's Alpha value is 0.788. Thus, the Cronbach's Alpha value is >0.60 so that the instrument is declared reliable. The orientation rating scale used in this study is a five (5) point Likert scale according to the rules and characteristics of the scales as shown in the Table 3.

Table 1. Distribution of study samples

Variable	Group	Total	Percentage (%)
Gender	Man	62	48.8
	Women	65	51.2
	Total	127	100
Background education	Elementary and intermediate	24	18.9
	University	103	81.1
	Total	127	100
Age	<20 Years	68	53.5
	20-30 years	36	28.3
	>30 Years	23	18.1
	Total	127	100

Table 2. List of instrument item validity

No	Instrument items	Total	Table	Information
1	I prefer learning Arabic through YouTube	0.596	0.1743	Valid
2	Learning Arabic through YouTube is fun	0.766	0.1743	Valid
3	I get the motivation to learn Arabic through YouTube	0.757	0.1743	Valid
4	Every day I make time to access the Dars Arabi channel	0.637	0.1743	Valid
5	The method used on the Dars Arabi channel is easy	0.591	0.1743	Valid
6	The material contained on the Dars Arabi channel matches my Arabic level	0.571	0.1743	Valid
7	Arabic exercises on the Dars Arabi channel vary	0.598	0.1743	Valid
8	My Arabic language skills are still relatively weak	0.207	0.1743	Valid
9	In learning Arabic, i feel it is enough to use the Dars Arabi channel	0.702	0.1743	Valid
10	My Arabic language skills improved after studying on the Dars Arabi channel	0.527	0.1743	Valid

Table 3. Key to the rating scale

Orientation level				
Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Not at all
5	4	3	2	1

Based on the scale value in the Table 3, the average value found in this study is based on the (1):

$$\frac{(5-1)}{3} = \frac{(4)}{3} = 1.33 \quad (1)$$

highest score to lowest score: number of levels. So: the lowest level is 1.00 to 2.33, medium level: 2.34 to 3.67, and highest level: 3.68 to 5. The variables in this study are divided into two types; the independent variables consisted of the sex of the respondent (2 groups; male and female), the age of the respondent (3 groups; less than 20 years, between 20 to 30 years, and more than 30 years), and educational background (2 groups; middle schools and colleges). The second type of variable is dependence, namely the tendency of the YouTube user channel Dars Arabi in learning Arabic as shown by the sample and the whole questionnaire items. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive statistical analysis, which describes or provides an overview of the object under study through a sample or population as it is without analyzing and making general conclusions [23]. The data presented include the presentation of frequency and percentage tables to provide a clear picture of the problem under study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. The tendency of Arabic learners through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi

To determine Arabic learners' tendency through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi, determine can do it by calculating the average and standard deviation of the respondents' responses to each questionnaire item. This is as explained in the Table 4. Table 4 shows that Arabic learners' tendency through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi shows an average ranging from (4.5118-3.0236). In contrast, the total average trend of YouTube users is (3.8559) in the medium group. The highest average is shown in item (5), namely (4.5118) with a standard deviation (0.6530) which belongs to the high-level group with the grain text that reads (The method used on the Dars Arabi channel is easy). The second level is shown in item (7), namely (4.3150) with a standard deviation (0.7528) which is included in the high-level group also with the grain text that reads (Arabic exercises on the Dars Arabi channel vary). The third level is shown in item (10), namely (4.1654) with a standard deviation (0.8616) which is included in the high-level group, as well as the item text that reads (My Arabic skills improved after studying on the Dars Arabi channel).

The most recent level is indicated by item (4) with a mean (3.0236) and standard deviation (0.9038). This item belongs to the moderate average group. The sound of the item is (Every day, I make time to access the Dars Arabi channel). Wang and Chen [24] assessed that people's tendency to obtain information from YouTube was based on a high level of curiosity about the issues they were facing, such as looking for answers to stored concerns, comparing information obtained from two sources such as YouTube and other media, or simply looking for inspiration or fun. Thus, learning content presented using YouTube media became a new market for Arabic language learners to learn from online resources.

YouTube is considered to be one of the most effective media for online learning. Halim *et al.* [25] revealed that YouTube is a web site that may qualify to promote digitally generated learning that requires simultaneous input. YouTube is the most popular video-based medium nowadays. Despite that, the video itself is not useful learning material; it still needs a concept from a teacher that is in line with the purpose of learning.

Table 4. Mean and standard deviation of the responses of research respondents

No	Instrument items	Average	Standard deviation	Level	Trends
5	The method used on the Dars Arabi channel is easy	4.5118	0.6530	1	High
7	Arabic exercises on the Dars Arabi channel vary	4.3150	0.7528	2	High
10	My Arabic language skills improved after studying on the Dars Arabi channel	4.1654	0.8616	3	High
6	The material contained on the Dars Arabi channel matches my Arabic level	4.1339	0.8103	4	High
2	Learning Arabic through YouTube is fun	4.0945	0.8011	5	High
3	I get the motivation to learn Arabic through YouTube	3.7402	0.9530	6	Moderate
8	My Arabic language skills are still relatively weak	3.6850	1.0134	7	Moderate
1	I prefer learning Arabic through YouTube	3.5118	0.8439	8	Moderate
9	In learning Arabic, I feel it is enough to use the Dars Arabi channel	3.3780	1.0152	9	Low
4	Every day I make time to access the Dars Arabi channel	3.0236	0.9038	10	Low
	Total	3.8559	0.8608		

Mature planning in line with learning goals and the integration of YouTube videos as a support tool can optimize learning outcomes because they align with the learning style and interests of the digital generation. Burke added that YouTube can also increase students' interest in learning and support the learning style of the generation of learners in this era, as well as provide learning experiences about the use of new technologies that will be useful after they graduate.

3.2. The correlation between the average respondents' responses to the questionnaire items and the Dars Arabi channel's tendency is based on gender, educational background, and age

To find out the correlation between the average respondents' responses to the questionnaire items and Arabic learners' tendency through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi, researchers did it by calculating the average respondents' responses to the questionnaire items and the total standard deviation. Then it is associated with the tendency of YouTube users to learn Arabic based on variables of gender, age, and educational background. This can be explained in the Table 5. In Table 5, it is found that there is a difference between the average respondent's responses to the questionnaire items and the tendency of Arabic learners through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi based on gender, educational background, and age variables. To determine the significance of the difference between the two, calculations are carried out using the three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), as in Table 6.

In Table 6 are found: i) the significance value for the student gender variable is obtained (0.200), which explains that the significance is higher than the significance ($\alpha = 0.05$). This shows no significant difference between the average respondents' responses to the questionnaire items and the tendency of Arabic learners through the Dars Arabi YouTube video channel related to the student gender variable; ii) The educational background variable's significance value is (0.320), which means it is higher than the significance level, namely ($\alpha = 0.05$). This shows no significant difference between the mean score of respondents on the questionnaire items in total with the tendency of Arabic learners through Arabic media videos on YouTube channel Dars Arabi which is related to educational background variables; and iii) the age variable's significant value is (0.208), which explains that the significance is higher than the significance level, namely ($\alpha = 0.05$). This also shows no significant difference between the average respondents' responses to the questionnaire items and the tendency of Arabic learners through the Dars Arabi YouTube video channel related to the age variable. Sources of significant differences related to the age variable of YouTube channel users can be through the following Table 7.

Table 5. Correlation of mean and standard deviation with variables

Variable	Group	Average	Standard deviation
Gender	Man	3.8274	0.47431
	Women	3.8831	0.54215
	Total	3.8559	0.50891
Educational background	Elementary and intermediate	3.8083	0.42418
	University	3.8670	0.52792
	Total	3.8559	0.50891
Age	<20 years	3.9059	0.44146
	20-30 years	3.8444	0.58965
	>30 years	3.7261	0.55777
	Total	3.8559	0.50891

Table 6. Triple variant analysis of the average respondent's response to the questionnaire items and the tendency of Arabic learners through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi with variables (gender, educational background, and age)

Variable	Sum of total squares	Degrees of freedom	Average squared	F value	Significance
Gender	0.429	1	0.429	1.660	0.200
Educational background	0.257	1	0.257	0.996	0.320
Age	0.823	2	0.411	1.591	0.208
Error	29.718	115			
Total	1920.870	127			

Table 7. Comparison of the mean value of respondents with the tendency of Arabic learners through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi according to the age variable

Variable	Group	Average	The value of the difference between the two means	
			20-30 Years	>30 Years
Age	<20 Years	3.9059	0.06144	0.17980
	20-30 Years	3.8444		0.11836
	>30 Years	3.7261	-0.11836	

In Table 7, it is found that there is no significant difference between the responses of students who are less than 20 years old, up to 30 years old, and more than 30 years old. The highest significance is in the group of YouTube users who are less than 20 years of age. This shows that YouTube users who are over 30 years of age, their tendency to learn Arabic through the YouTube channel Dars Arabi is greater than the other two groups.

Changes in the pattern of learning, including learning Arabic, especially in the situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, have made learning Arabic online a new habit for many learners. Learners seem more enthusiastic in following the Arabic learning process when presented. The presentation of learning content on the Dars Arabi channel generally ends with an exercise in mastering the material or skills for learner understanding which was responded to by the Dars Arabi channel management team. Through the platform, teachers must pay attention to the language education of learners by providing language assignment exercises to strengthen their understanding and language skills [26].

Based on the analysis of data on Arabic learners' trends through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi, in general, Arabic learners are at a high average level. Users of the Dars Arabi channel YouTube media think that the Dars Arabi channel method is easy. Likewise, Arabic exercises on the channel vary. In general, Dars Arabi channel YouTube media users also feel that their Arabic language skills have improved after learning Arabic from the channel. In terms of learning material content on the Dars Arabi channel, they consider that the Dars Arabi channel's learning materials follow their Arabic level. Likewise, most of the respondents stated that learning Arabic through YouTube is fun. A high average level indicates the five points above, affecting their language skills after learning Arabic online through the Dars Arabi YouTube channel.

The findings above are following the research results [27], which shows that YouTube can be used as a learning medium that provides wide opportunities in both formal and informal language learning. These results are also in line with research findings [28] which show that the use of YouTube videos can positively influence and motivate users to learn foreign languages. Whereas related to the finding that the Dars Arabi YouTube media has a variety of language training and Arabic language material, this is under the results of research [29], which shows that online-based learning materials can support foreign language learners in obtaining the latest information and describing the target language. As for Dars Arabi's learning method channels learning method, which YouTube media users widely use, learning a language will feel easy if it is done with pleasure. Learning models such as Dars Arabi are one of the efforts to answer the challenges of developing distance learning models in addition to other models [30], [31].

The subsequent data analysis results show that gender does not affect Arabic learners' tendency through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi. Between the sexes of males and females, YouTube users have almost the same tendency in viewing Arabic learning through YouTube media. Likewise, there is no significant difference when seen from the age variable where the three age groups tend to learn Arabic through the YouTube video media channel Dars Arabi. The variables affect the formation of their tendency towards learning Arabic through YouTube media.

Research conducted by Ritonga *et al.* [32] shows that remote Arabic learning can use YouTube as a learning medium so that the material delivered is understandable, easy to understand, and enjoyable for learners, so that brands can easily focus on the learning delivered by teachers. Moreover, Arabic is a foreign language that requires deep focus and rigor to absorb the meaning of learning from a teacher. Thus, the YouTube media breakthrough sparked by the Dars Arabi account became an option for Arabic learners of all ages.

The findings above differ from the trend towards making YouTube videos. Research by Vedantham's [33] study shows that there are significant differences between the sexes of men and women in terms of making YouTube videos. More males than females. The results show that there is no significant difference associated with students' different educational backgrounds with research findings [34], which shows that there are significant differences in the use of social media. The findings above, which show that age does not affect the tendency to learn Arabic through YouTube media, are in line with the findings of Tahir *et al.* [35] study, which shows that YouTube media users include all age layers.

Based on the explanation above, this study declares the implications of the use of YouTube Dars Arabic in learning Arabic. YouTube media has good relevance for Arabic language learners to enhance their listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills through a number of materials studied on the YouTube platform. However, the role of teachers in face-to-face learning cannot be replaced by YouTube media, as teachers provide the equivalence, discipline, figure, and noble character that cannot be acquired through YouTube accounts. Therefore, Arabic language learners can adopt materials from YouTube media such as Dars Arabic and are still advised to do direct learning with their tutors.

4. CONCLUSION

According to the results of the quantitative data analysis presented above, the researchers discovered that Arabic learners' inclination towards the Dars Arabi YouTube video channel was at a moderately average level. The highest group of respondents is predominantly represented by the average value of the items used in the method employed on the Dars Arabi channel. The Arabic language training provided on the Dars Arabi channel covers a range of skills, and the content is tailored to the Arabic proficiency level of YouTube users. It is enjoyable to acknowledge that individuals acquire knowledge of the Arabic language by utilizing YouTube. A high average level of proficiency in Arabic language skills is observed in individuals who utilize the Dars Arabi channel on YouTube, resulting in a positive impact of five points above the baseline. The results of the quantitative data analysis indicate that the gender, educational background, and age of YouTube users have no impact on their inclination towards learning Arabic online. The findings of this study demonstrate the imperative of incorporating YouTube media into language learning, as it can be utilized by individuals from all strata of society in an enjoyable and laid-back manner. Furthermore, it serves as a platform for acquiring knowledge in Arabic, a language that has yet to fully exploit media platforms like YouTube and other online channels. Utilizing media in the process of learning Arabic can bring Arabic in line with other foreign languages that are acknowledged by the United Nations. The research focus is restricted to the subscribers' trend of the Dars Arabi YouTube channel. Future researchers can explore various other themes related to this topic by analyzing additional online learning channel messages on YouTube and considering broader variables. Hence, the researchers propose that the subsequent investigation assess the efficacy of Arabic acquisition via the YouTube platform for individuals who are not native speakers, while considering variables such as age groups, educational history, employment, and motivation. This study will offer extensive information regarding the level of importance and immediacy of Arabic distance education through the YouTube platform.

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